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Indian knowledge System with Reference to Ajanta Elora Caves and Lord Gautam Buddha and his Teachings

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Abstract:

Indian Knowledge System is relevant in contemporary scenario because new generation is forgetful about old traditions, customs and archeological monuments. Communal frenzy, terrorism, loss of moral values, crimes, suicides, depression are prevalent in some parts of our nation. So it is the need of hour to follow Indian knowledge System. The opening chapters of Atharva veda and Rig veda describes universal brotherhood (Vasudev kutumbkam). Upanishads are full of moral teachings. A person may lead a medicine free life by practicing yoga and meditation. Yoga has been mentioned in Patanjali Yog Sutra and vedas. Today's students have Fabia of Sanskrit language but students should be inspired to comprehend , acquire knowledge, learn Sanskrit language and take interest in Sanskrit language. It is the oldest classical language . It is the most technical language. Its grammar is systematic, scientific and flawless . It will be an excellent academic journey to learn and speak Sanskrit. This paper highlights Ajanta Elora caves and its relation to Indian Knowledge System. This paper focuses also on life and teachings of *Gautam Buddha*.

Keywords: *Moral, Ethical, Indian Knowledge System, Caves, Buddhism.*

Introduction:

Ajanta caves are situated nearby 101 kilometres from Sambhajinagar. These are built out of black stones and given the shape of huge horse. These caves are best examples of archeology, artistry, craft. Gautam Buddha's statue is having rabbits under it. There is Buddhist monastery , monks come to visit here and study Gautam Buddha's teachings. Monks worship here. Carvings are based on life of Gautam Buddha. These carvings express Jatak tales and stories of previous birth of Gautam Buddha. Caves were not discovered for 700 years but British army official John Smith explored these caves during 1816. The caves appear to be U shapes over all. Mineral colours are used to make these carvings beautiful.

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Review of Literature:

The sources of my research are books and different web sources. I visited the tourist place and the survey was completed with the help of a guide. The research was completed with the help of newspapers.

Objectives:

The objectives of my research are as follows:

- To equip new generation with richness of Indian Knowledge System.
- To learn philosophy and teachings of Lord Gautam Buddha.
- To Promote innovation and research in this field of study
- To enlighten our life and society.
- To promote Indian Knowledge System among students and research scholars.

Research Methodology :

I applied qualitative methods to complete my research work. I surveyed various people to give a new aura to my research.

The caves are carved out of flood basalt and granite rock of a cliff. This monument is listed in UNESCO world heritage list. There are 29 caves in Ajanta. Out of which caves 9, 10, 12, 26, 29 are places of worship. Rest of the caves famous for ashram. The stone discovery took four centuries of hard work. These excavations were performed by Vakatak kings.

These caves are world famous. Tourists come from Italy, US and UK and other European countries.

These caves are peculiar because the artisans started their artistry from top to bottom. These carvings express the perseverance, devotion and determination of artisans. These caves are devoted to Gautam Buddha for worship. Monasteries were centre of meditation and preachings of Gautam Buddha. The carvings of walls express man from birth to death, King to slave, rich to poor, saint to wicked, compassionate to cruel, love to hate, delight to sorrow, victory to defeat and so on innumerable images.

The images here described are court, village, town, big mansions and ashramas. People come to know about costumes, jewellery, music, utensils, weapons used in war. These paintings are about flowers, fruits, birds and animals. Before painting the walls were applied prime coat or base coat. Cave no 5 is called Mahamandap and Theravada cave. Its area is 36 metres and 18 metres. The monks used it as a hub of education and dining hall.

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Cave no 6 has statue of Saraswati. The goddess Saraswati is called Mahamayuri in Buddhist religion.

Cave no 11 has statue of Lord Ganesh on the entrance. Along with it is carvings of Kubera Yaksh and Mahesh Mahadev. These are the artistry of Ellora.

Cave no 17 has the carvings of Lord Brahma, Vishnu. Some of the carvings include goddess Durga and Shalmanjika.

Cave no 18, 19 have a shivling.

Cave 20 has carvings of girls.

Cave no 21 has Rameshwaram. It has bullock Nandi in front of cave. Inside cave the carving of Ganga sitting on crocodile. One of the jyotirling is there.

Daulatabad fort was constructed by Bhilamraj in 1187. There is Chand temple in Daulatabad. Marvellous tomb of Rabia-ul-Durrani wife of Aurangzeb having a grand door on it. Brass artistic work is ultimate. One fountain inside the tomb increases beauty of architecture. Jain caves are carved in Elora. These are away from Hindu and Buddha caves. Gautam Buddha's eight fold path can make our lives awesome. It is as follows: look good things always. Don't be tempted to unfair means. Utter sweet words not bitter ones. Don't murder anybody. Don't indulge in theft and sexual misbehaviour. Earn with right means. Don't be involved in making servant to others. Selling intoxicants and slaughtering animals. Enjoy your present, practice meditation.

Cave no. 5 is called Mahamuni and Theravada cave. Its area is 36 metres and 18 metres. The monks used it as a hub of education and dining hall.

Cave no. 6 has statue of Saraswati. This is the Goddess Saraswati is called Mahamayuri in Buddhist religion. Cave no. 11 has statue of Lord Ganesh on the entrance. Along with it is carvings of Kubera, Yaksh and Maheshwari. These are the artistry of Ellora.

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Gautam Buddha was born in c. 563 and achieved salvation in 483 BCE. He was born in Lumbini present Nepal. His childhood name was Siddhartha. He was born in a royal family his father was a monarch called Shuddhodana of the Shakya dynasty and Queen Maya. He got married to Yashodhara and the couple got a baby boy Rahula. Four incidents changed his life an old man, an ill person, a dead body, aged person, a wandering saint. He denounced worldly life and married life in search of answers to human sorrows. At the age of 35 he became a saint and Buddha.

He gave his first preaching in Sarnath. His teachings include sympathy, pity, non violence, calm and quiet. He told us not to desire things in excess. It may give us unhappiness. He got enlightened under a pipal tree in Bodhgaya, Bihar in search of truth. He achieved moksha at the age 80 in Kushinagar India.

Buddhism is spread in east and Southeast Asia in Thailand, China, Cambodia, Japan, Bhutan, India, Myanmar, Shrilanka, Laos, Mongolia, Korea, Vietnam and Singapore. 10 million people in India follow Buddhist religion, only 1% in India our country.

Hindi language is significant not only in India but in the world scenario. London is multi lingual city. People may keep their culture alive only through the means of language. Hindi is taught to Children at home living in London. Parents make their children learn not only Hindi language but they teach Ramayan, Mahabharat hindi poems in London also.

The language Hindi is taught in 176 universities in the world. Not only Indians learn it but native people also learn Hindi abroad. Schools are run between age group of 7 to 14 years during weekend to teach in Hindi in USA. High school children are taught in Hindi medium in USA. Kavi Sammelan, get togethers are organised to promote Hindi. Children learn Hindi to communicate parents in USA. Ramlila is performed in Singapore. also Dipawali and Holi is celebrated with fervour and enthusiasm in USA and Singapore.

Self realization is a prominent part of our life. Meditation increases our memory as Yoga. Meditation is realising every part of our body. It energises us as Yoga. It is through meditation that we feel presence of god. One person feels calm, and quiet and peaceful during meditation. Meditation removes our depression and the person is more focussed, and concentrated strongly and it improves mental health. While meditating focus on breath and enchant mantras.

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Findings:

A person must do self realization to enjoy and be delightful!

धर्मो धर्मो सुख दुःखं मानसानि न ते विभो। न कर्तासि न भोक्तासि मुक्त एपासि सर्वदा

The meaning of shloka is Qualities and bad habits. sorrow and joy are of the mind , not of you, O all - pervading one . You are neither man of action nor taking pleasure. A man is always free .Astovaka Samhita describes dialogue between the saint and Janaka king of Mithila. Astrvakra Samhita talks about Advet Vedanta and self realisation.

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